

Investigation of the Influence of a Magnetic Field on the Flow Field and Gas Bubble Evolution in an Electrolytic Cell

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Keywords: Lorentz force, electrochemical machining, NaNO₃-electrolyte, particle image velocimetry, magnetohydrodynamic simulation, multiphase simulation

Abstract

Pulsed electrochemical machining (PECM) is increasingly seen as a key technology for advancing the miniaturization, efficiency and functional enhancement of components. Ongoing research indicates that the application of a magnetic field can modify the electrochemical process. Although the effects of various process parameters - such as pulse settings, flow dynamics and choice of cathode material - are largely understood, the specific role of magnetic fields in process optimization remains elusive. This study aims to deepen our understanding of magnetic field assisted electrochemical machining, focusing in particular on the effects of the Lorentz force within a NaNO₃ electrolyte. An experimental setup was created to position the magnetic field perpendicular to the electrode surfaces, and a significant gap was maintained between the aluminum electrodes to minimize the effect of the electrochemical reaction on the flow of the electrolyte. The flow, which is primarily driven by the Lorentz force in the static liquid, was modelled using magnetohydrodynamic and multiphase simulations and then analyzed using particle image velocimetry and shadowgraphy. These simulations were validated against the experimental results. In the future, this simulation-based methodology will be extended to scenarios such as electrochemical machining with pulsed electric currents and vibrating cathodes.

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1 Introduction

The rising need for materials that are both high-strength and challenging to machine, combined with the demand for high precision in manufacturing, has led to more stringent specifications for designing the relevant manufacturing processes. Electrochemical machining (ECM) and its derivatives, like pulsed electrochemical machining (PECM), stand out for their ability to fulfill these requirements [1–5].

By customizing the shape of the cathode, adjusting the pulsing patterns, and choosing appropriate electrolytes and flow conditions, it's possible to precisely control the rate of material removal, the accuracy of the machining, and the resulting surface smoothness [6][7].

A literature review reveals that a superimposed magnetic field offers the potential to influence electrochemical processes [8–11] such as electrochemical metal deposition by increasing depletion rates [12–14] and to enhance the detachment of hydrogen bubbles from the electrodes, which results in more efficient machining [15–17].

The present study continues the research on the fundamentals of magnetic field assisted electrochemical machining (ECM) discussed in [18] (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, Step 1). Already validated simulation and measurement methods are applied, which are transferred to a geometry modeled on a flow channel in ECM (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, Step 2).

Figure 1: General approach to analyze superposition of magnetic field and ECM by measurements and numeric simulation models. Step 1: Starting with a simplified measuring cell (present work). Step 2: Transfer to a mesoscale analysis cell, to analyze the influence of

the magnetic field in a measurable scale. Step 3: Investigation within the actual ECM-process.

The main objective is to identify and understand the interactions between the external magnetic field, the macroscopic flow of the sodium nitrate electrolyte in the working gap and the formation and propagation of reaction gases such as oxygen and hydrogen. In a last step (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, Step 3), the influence of the magnetic field on the ECM-process and machining results will be investigated in the actual ECM machining process.

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental Setup

A 3D-model of the optical measuring cell is shown in Figure 2. In preliminary investigations in which the wall was flush with the cell geometry, there were flow interactions with the wall which impaired the reproducibility of the results. Hence, in this setup the cell is placed into a large acrylic glass container with the dimensions 250 mm × 100 mm × 100 mm with a wall thickness of 2 mm.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the measuring cell.

This setup enables optical accessibility and interference-free flow propagation. The cell was made by additive manufacturing (material: polylactide) and consists out of two vertically aligned pockets which are housing the magnets and the electrodes. Between the pockets is the interelectrode gap (working gap) with a height of 10 mm. The electrode of the bottom pocket is a 0.5 mm thin aluminum wire embedded in epoxy resin to avoid stray currents. It serves as the cathode. The exchangeable aluminum anode has a length of 16 mm and a diameter of 5 mm. Once inserted in the upper pocket it provides a watertight seal to the area where the magnet is

located, and the electrical contact is enabled. Around the anode, a recess was created which directs the uprising gas bubbles away from the reaction zone and into a tube leading out of the pocket where further measurements can take place if required. An aqueous solution with sodium nitrate (9.5 % mass fraction, balance for mixing: LC 1200 S, Sartorius AG) is used as electrolyte. The cell is filled with approximately 2l of electrolyte. The permanent magnets are made of neodymium, iron, and boron (NdFeB N45) and has a dimension of 36 mm in length and 18 mm in width. Their distance to each other is 42 mm resulting in a 16 mm distance from the working gap. Table 1 summarizes the parameters of the electrolyte and magnets.

To create different magnitudes of the Lorentz force, the electric current is varied by using a variable constant current power source (EA-PSI 5080-20 A, EA-Elektro-Automatik GmbH). Measurements of the magnetic flux were conducted on the magnet surface and in the working gap using a magnetic flux meter (PCE-MFM 3000-ICA, PCE Instruments™).

Table 1: Parameters of the experimental setup.

Electrolyte	
Mixture	9.5 m% NaNO ₃ 90.5 m% H ₂ O
Density	1.065 kg/m ³
Kinematic viscosity	0.95 · 10 ⁻⁶ m ² /s
Dynamic viscosity	0.00102 Pa·s
Electric conductivity	7 S/m
Magnet	
Material	NdFeB N45
Magnetic flux density	0.250 T
Length	36 mm
Width	18 mm
Height	4 mm
Quantity	2

Stereo Particle image velocimetry (SPIV) is used to investigate the electrolyte flow in the examination area. The SPIV system consists of two CCD cameras (LaVision Imager CX5) mounted on Scheimpflug adapters and a 532 nm double-pulse laser (TSI, YAG200-15-LIT:

Nd:YAG, max. power per pulse: 1200 mJ; repetition rate: 15 Hz; max. pulse duration 4 ns). All images are processed with the software Da-Vis (Version 10.2.1, LaVision).

Shadowgraphy is used to characterize the evolving hydrogen bubbles from the cathode in terms of quantity, size, and velocity. The System consists out of a CCD camera (LaVision Imager CX5) and a light source (LaVision Flashlight Inspec). For a depth of field calibration, a calibration plate is moved step by step through the examination area by a translation stage (Optos Sigma: OSMS26-100). The supplied electrical charge is monitored by a data acquisition unit (Fluke 2638A Hydro Series 3).

2.3 Simulation approach

The simulation area only includes the electrolyte in the working gap.

The simulation approach provides for the division into two consecutive individual simulations. The first simulation model addresses the calculation of the electromagnetic fields and consequently the Lorentz force in the working gap. This Lorentz force distribution in the working gap is exported as the result of the first simulation and implemented in the second simulation as an effective volume force. Within this second simulation, the magnetohydrodynamics are then combined with a multiphase flow as a result of the hydrogen gas production. The numerical method is based on an Eulerian-Eulerian model. It is implemented as a two-way coupled lattice Boltzmann-Finite Volume method in the multiphysics solver environment m-AIA (multiphysics-Aerodynamisches Institut Aachen) of the AIA. The magnetic forces that were determined in the MHD simulations are incorporated as additional forcing terms in the LB solver, representing the liquid phase. The method was successfully used in the previous study [18]. A more thorough description of the method can be found that work and in [20]. The gas mass flow is directly proportional to the applied electrical current density, which is a result of the first simulation.

The solid areas are modeled using appropriate boundary conditions. For this purpose and based on the experiment, an electrical current of 20 mA is defined at the cathode. The anode has an electrical potential of 0 V. The solid container wall and the insulation are modeled by a no-slip boundary condition. The magnetic field is defined using a magnetic vector potential.

Due to the paramagnetic materials used, no significant influence on the magnetic field lines can be assumed, so that a homogeneous field is present. To ensure comparable initial states between the experiment and the simulation, the magnetic flux density in the working gap was measured using the PCE-MFM 3000-ICA magnetic field meter from PCE Instruments™. The value determined in this way is approx. 50 mT. The largest gradients of the electromagnetic field quantities are to be expected in areas close to the electrode surfaces. At the same time, it can be assumed that the effect of the Lorentz force is more pronounced in the area between the electrodes than in the outer wall areas. For these reasons, the mesh was significantly more refined in these areas. Figure 3 shows the derived mesh for the calculation of the electromagnetic field within the electrolyte domain. The total number of tetrahedron-volume-elements is 3.314.891.

Figure 3: Derived mesh for the calculation of the electromagnetic fields and Lorentz force.

3 Results

3.1 Electromagnetic fields and Lorentz force

Figure 4 shows the magnitude of the electric current density J within the z - x - and z - y -plane. The red color represents regions with high values. The false color legend has a logarithmic scaling. It can be seen that in the area close to the electrodes, the values increase over $1,000 \text{ A/m}^2$. The distribution is strongly inhomogeneous. Due to its low conductivity of approx. 7 S/m , the electrolyte acts as a strong ohmic resistor. If the distance between the anode and cathode increases, the total resistance and thus the voltage drop increases and the electrical current density decreases. Therefore, a very strong decrease can be observed in the direction of the outer container wall.

Figure 4: Magnitude of the electric current density in z - x - and z - y -plane.

Figure 5 shows the Lorentz force density within the z - x - and z - y -plane. The Lorentz force is calculated by the cross product between the electric current density and the magnetic flux density. As a result, the Lorentz force density values are high towards the electrodes but shows significant bigger values within the area close to the cathode. Maximum values are approx. 50 N/m^3 . The strong inhomogeneity is not only due to the field distribution of the electric current density, but also to the path of the electric and magnetic field lines. As such, the field lines in front of the electrodes are at a large angle to each other.

Figure 5: Magnitude of the Lorentz force density in z - x - and z - y -plane.

3.2 Flow field and bubble distribution

In Figure 6 the liquid velocity field of the multiphase simulations with magnetic forces is shown. The two forces driving the liquid velocity field are due to the interaction of the liquid with the buoyant gas bubbles and the Lorentz forces. The effects of these forces can be seen in the components of the velocity field. The w -velocity (perpendicular to the slice plane) is driven

only by the Lorentz force field. Two counterrotating vortices around the two electrodes that correspond to the orientation of the Lorentz forces can be identified. In the center of the domain some components of the lower vortex are transported along with the rising bubbles and interact with the upper vortex.

Figure 6: Components of the liquid velocity field of the multiphase simulations with Lorentz forces.

In the other two velocity components effects of both driving forces are visible. In the lower half of the domain a region of negative v-velocity due to the strong vortex around the lower cathode is surrounding the area of positive v-velocity that is caused by the rising bubbles.

3.3 Stereo PIV-Measurements of flow field

Figure 7 shows the scalar flow field inside the working gap of the measurement cell. For the U-component, the position of the electrodes and the direction of the magnetic and electric field is schematically illustrated.

Figure 7: Scalar flow field of the working gap, superimposed with a magnetic field and divided in U-, V- and W-velocity component.

Without magnetic field, the overall velocities are close to zero with maximum absolute values of 0.0013 m/s. Main driver of convection are the uprising bubbles. The image processing was challenging due to the reflections of the rising bubbles, which is why white areas in the graphic indicate missing data points. Superimposition of the magnetic field causes two counter rotating vortex flows. The spin direction is derived from the U- and W-component. Hence, the upper vortex rotates clockwise, and the bottom

vortex rotates counterclockwise around the vertical Y-axis. The upper vortex flow appears weaker which is probable due to the larger active electrode area of the anode, resulting in a reduced current density. Maximum absolute velocities reach up to 0.0088 m/s. The U- and V-components indicate besides the two vortices around the vertical axis, secondary flow behavior, resulting in a downward stream onto the cathode.

3.4 Gas bubble visualization

Figure 8 shows the evolution of hydrogen bubbles with increasing Voltage from 3 V to 10 V. At around 3 V the cell Voltage results in the transmission of electric current and therefore in the evolution of hydrogen bubbles at the cathode.

Figure 8: Hydrogen bubbles evolving from the cathode at applied voltages from 3 V to 10 V with superimposed magnetic field.

The average size of the bubbles, shown in Figure 9 increases from bubbles of below 0.05 mm up until bubbles of 0.3 mm in diameter. With the increasing bubble size, the bubble velocity also increases, leading to velocities in the range of 0.01 m/s to 0.06 m/s.

Figure 9: Comparison of the bubble size between shadowgraphy measurements with and without a superimposed magnetic field

With increasing electric current until 20 mA, the bubble diameter increases. With voltages up

to approx. 5 V, the bubble detachment is promoted resulting in smaller bubbles with a narrow size distribution which is consistent with the results of [21] and [22]. With increasing voltage and electric current, the detachment of bubbles from the cathode was adversely affected by the magnetic field, presumably contributing to the observed higher cell voltage. This behavior is consistent with the work of [22] and [17] demonstrating the opposite effect at microelectrodes with a diameter of 125 μm in their studies. The magnetic field has a stabilizing effect on the gas bubble production. Given that the cathode in this work has a diameter of 500 μm , a similar stabilizing effect seems to occur. According to [22] the vertical secondary flow onto the electrode induced through the vortex (see Figure 7) is not the main reason for the increased bubble detachment time, rather the detachment mechanism itself is influenced.).

4 Summary and Conclusions.

In this work, the influence of a magnetic field superposition on the flow field and the gas bubble behaviour in an electrolysis process between two cathodes was investigated using simulations and experiments. The process was intended to represent an abstracted ECM setup. The simulation methods used included the FVM to calculate the electromagnetic fields and the Lorentz force as a significant interaction and the Lattice Boltzmann FVM to calculate the multiphase flow field. The experimental and in particular metrological methods used were stereo PIV to determine the flow fields and shadowgraphy to assess the formation and distribution of gas bubbles.

The results show that the flow field can be significantly influenced by the superposition of a magnetic field. It should be noted that the highly inhomogeneous Lorentz force results in an equally highly inhomogeneous flow field. This means that in areas of high Lorentz force, the electrolyte flow follows the force effect well. This observation is supported by the PIV measurements. Furthermore, the multiphase simulation showed that a high flow velocity can be expected in the middle region of the working gap due to rising gas bubbles. This result was initially not confirmed by the PIV measurements. Additional shadowgraphy studies then confirmed the flow predicted by the simulation by visualising the gas bubbles and their motion.

Declarations

Acknowledgement and Funding

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) within the priority program SPP 2231 – project no. 422633203.

Conflicts of interest / Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Availability of data, material, and code

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time due to technical or time limitations.

Ethics approval

The work contains no libelous or unlawful statements, does not infringe on the rights of others, or contain material or instructions that might cause harm or injury.

Consent to participate

The authors consent to participate.

Consent for publication

The authors consent to publish.

Authors Contribution

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